

Co-funded by
the European Union

SEISC
Sustainable
Entrepreneurship
in Smart Clothing

Framework of competences for the students' "Sustainable Entrepreneurial Mindset"

Partner Coordinator
OpenCom (IT)

November 2024

Project Name:	SEiSC – Sustainable entrepreneurship in smart clothing		
WP	WP3 - Case study development		
TASK	WP3.1 - A framework of competences for the students’ “Sustainable entrepreneurial mindset”		
SUB-TASK	3.1.7. Finalize the Framework of Competences		
Deliverable	RESULT 3.1: FRAMEWORK OF COMPETENCES FOR THE STUDENTS’ “SUSTAINABLE ENTREPRENEURIAL MINDSET”		
Date:	24/11/2024	Release:	Final
Authors:	Erina Guraziu, Phd; Rodrigo Latorre Vivar, Phd		
Owner:	OpenCom		
Project Coordinator	Lounais-Hämeen koulutuskuntayhtymä		
Deliverable Version:	Version 1.0		
Distribution	LHKK, 24/11/2024		
Approved	LHKK, 25/11/2024		
Distribution	Website, 28/11/2024		

Table of Contents

Development of the Sustainable Entrepreneurial Mindset Framework for Secondary Education.. 5

Introduction	5
Objectives	5
Theoretical Foundations	5
Learning Outcomes Oriented Approach.....	5
Experiential Learning.....	6
EntreComp Framework.....	8
GreenComp Framework.....	9
Bloom’s taxonomy.....	11
Methodology	13
1. Framework Integration.....	13
2. Structural Design.....	13
3. Learning Progression.....	14
4. Learning Outcomes Definition.....	14
5. Integration of EntreComp and GreenComp.....	14
6. Alignment with Student Capabilities.....	15
7. Alignment with Bloom's Taxonomy.....	15
8. Development of Virtual Simulation Platform.....	15
9. Scenario Development.....	15
10. Iterative Refinement.....	16
Challenges and Solutions	16
Preliminary Reflections	16
References	16

Framework for Sustainable Entrepreneurial Mindset in Secondary Education19

1. Design Thinking & Sustainability Values	19
Initial (Understand).....	19
Intermediate (Analyze).....	19
Advanced (Create).....	19
2. Business Model Generation & Embracing Complexity	20
Initial (Understand).....	20
Intermediate (Analyze).....	20
Advanced (Create).....	20
3. Into Action & Acting for Sustainability	21
Initial (Understand).....	21
Intermediate (Analyze).....	21
Advanced (Create).....	21
4. Ideas & Opportunities & Envisioning Sustainable Futures	22
Initial (Understand).....	22
Intermediate (Analyze).....	22
Advanced (Create).....	22
5. Resources & Sustainability Complexity	23
Initial (Understand).....	23
Intermediate (Analyze).....	23
Advanced (Create).....	23

Development of the Sustainable Entrepreneurial Mindset Framework for Secondary Education

Introduction

This methodological note outlines the process of developing an innovative framework for fostering a Sustainable Entrepreneurial Mindset in secondary school students, along with a complementary Virtual Simulation Platform. The framework integrates key elements from the European Union's EntreComp (Entrepreneurship Competence Framework) and GreenComp (European sustainability competence framework), tailored specifically for the cognitive and developmental needs of secondary school students.

Objectives

The primary objective was to create a comprehensive framework that:

1. Combines entrepreneurial skills with sustainability competences in a way accessible to secondary students
2. Provides a clear progression of learning outcomes
3. Develops a practical application through a virtual simulation platform
4. Aligns with established educational theories and frameworks

Theoretical Foundations

The framework and simulation platform are grounded in several educational theories and concepts:

1. Bloom's Taxonomy: Informing the progression from understanding to analysis to creation.
2. Experiential Learning: Emphasizing hands-on, practical scenarios.
3. Constructivism: Encouraging students to build knowledge through active engagement.
4. Situated Learning: Providing context-rich scenarios in the smart clothing industry.

Learning Outcomes Oriented Approach

Learning outcomes-based approaches are grounded in constructivist theories of learning, which emerged as a significant paradigm shift in understanding how knowledge is acquired and competences are developed. Constructivism represents a departure from behaviorist theories that dominated educational thinking in the early 20th century, moving from a transmission model of education (input-based learning) to one where learners actively construct their understanding through experience and reflection (output-based learning). Learners actively construct knowledge and meaning through experiences, reflection, and social interaction (Vygotsky, 1978).

Vygotsky (1978) expanded this understanding through social constructivism, emphasizing the crucial role of social interaction in learning. His concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) highlighted how learners can achieve higher levels of understanding through guidance and collaboration with more capable peers or educators. This social dimension of learning has profound implications for how we understand competence development in educational and professional contexts.

The influence of constructivist theory is evident in how modern frameworks approach learning outcomes. For example, the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) reflects constructivist

principles in its emphasis on both individual capability development and the social context of learning. As noted by Cedefop (2017), this approach recognizes that competences are developed through active engagement in real-world contexts and through interaction with others.

According to the Council Recommendation of 22 May 2017, learning outcomes are defined as "statements of what a learner knows, understands and is able to do on completion of a learning process" (Council of the European Union, 2017, p. C189/15).

The approach is structured through qualifications frameworks that classify qualifications according to a set of criteria for specified levels of learning achieved. These frameworks aim to integrate and coordinate national qualifications subsystems while improving transparency, access, progression and quality of qualifications in relation to the labor market and civil society (Ibid).

The European Qualifications Framework (EQF) established eight reference levels, each defined by a set of descriptors indicating learning outcomes across three domains:

1. Knowledge - described as theoretical and/or factual, ranging from basic general knowledge (Level 1) to knowledge at the most advanced frontier of a field (Level 8)
2. Skills - described as cognitive (involving logical, intuitive and creative thinking) and practical (involving manual dexterity and use of methods, materials, tools and instruments), progressing from basic skills (Level 1) to the most advanced and specialized skills (Level 8)
3. Responsibility and autonomy - described as the ability to apply knowledge and skills with varying degrees of autonomy and responsibility, from working under direct supervision (Level 1) to demonstrating substantial authority, innovation, and scholarly integrity (Level 8)

The recommendation emphasizes that learning outcomes can be achieved through multiple pathways in formal, non-formal, or informal settings. This recognition is reflected in the qualification process, defined as "the formal outcome of an assessment and validation process by a competent authority" (Ibid).

The framework incorporates several key principles for implementing learning outcomes:

- Transparency: Clear description of what learners should achieve
- Comparability: Enabling comparison of qualifications across different systems and countries
- Transferability: Facilitating the transfer of qualifications between different contexts
- Recognition: Supporting the recognition of learning regardless of how or where it was acquired
- Progression: Enabling clear pathways for advancement in education and training

Experiential Learning

Experiential learning represents a crucial bridge between constructivist theories and practical competence development, offering a structured approach to understanding how learners develop capabilities through direct experience and reflection. This approach is particularly relevant for competence frameworks as it provides a theoretical foundation for understanding how learners develop complex capabilities through active engagement with real-world challenges.

The modern conception of experiential learning emerges directly from constructivist foundations. While Piaget (1976) established how learners construct knowledge through interaction with their environment, and Vygotsky (1978) emphasized the social dimension of learning, it was Kolb (1984) who synthesized these insights into a comprehensive theory of experiential learning. Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory (ELT) presents learning as a cyclical process where knowledge is created through the transformation of experience.

Kolb's experiential learning cycle consists of four stages:

1. Concrete Experience (feeling): Direct engagement with a new experience or situation
2. Reflective Observation (watching): Reflecting on the experience from multiple perspectives
3. Abstract Conceptualization (thinking): Forming new ideas and conclusions from the reflection
4. Active Experimentation (doing): Testing new concepts in new situations

This cycle aligns with Dewey's (1938) emphasis on the continuity of experience, where each learning experience builds upon previous ones and influences future experiences. Dewey's work established that not all experiences are equally educational, highlighting the importance of purposefully designed learning experiences that promote growth and development.

Schön (1983) further developed these ideas through his concept of the "reflective practitioner," introducing two crucial types of reflection:

- Reflection-in-action: Thinking while doing, making adjustments during the experience
- Reflection-on-action: Retrospective thinking about the experience and its outcomes

These theoretical foundations have significant implications for competence development. As noted by Boud, Cohen, and Walker (1993), experience alone does not lead to learning; it is the reflection on experience that generates meaningful learning outcomes. This understanding has led to the development of structured approaches to experiential learning in educational settings.

Jarvis (2006) expanded these concepts by emphasizing the transformative potential of experiential learning, particularly in adult education. His model shows how learners integrate their experiences with their biography, creating new understanding that transforms both the learner and their future interactions with the world.

Modern applications of experiential learning in competence development typically incorporate several key principles:

1. Whole-Person Learning (Kolb, 1984): Engaging cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains
2. Situated Learning (Lave & Wenger, 1991): Embedding learning in authentic contexts
3. Continuous Reflection (Schön, 1983): Integrating systematic reflection throughout the learning process
4. Active Experimentation (Kolb, 1984): Providing opportunities to test and apply new understanding
5. Social Interaction (Vygotsky, 1978): Incorporating collaborative learning and feedback

Moon (2004) has demonstrated how structured reflection can enhance experiential learning, particularly in professional and educational contexts. Her work shows how different levels of reflection contribute to deeper learning and the development of professional competences.

The integration of experiential learning principles in competence frameworks reflects what Mezirow (1991) terms "transformative learning," where learners develop not only new skills and knowledge but also new ways of understanding and interpreting their experiences. This transformation is essential for developing the complex competences required in modern professional contexts.

EntreComp Framework

EntreComp (Bacigalupo et al., 2016) is the Frameworks developed in 2016 by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission in response to 'A New Skills Agenda for Europe: working together to strengthen human capital, employability and competitiveness' (European Commission, 2016). The Agenda was created with the aim of targeting actions for the development of competences considered to be a challenge for the European Union, among them 'Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship' as a key competence of the 'Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning' (European Parliament and European Council, 2006). EntreComp, in fact, was created for the improvement of the entrepreneurial skills of European citizens and organisations, since, *'sense of initiative and entrepreneurship is a transversal key competence, which every citizen needs for personal fulfilment and development, active citizenship, social inclusion and employment in the knowledge society'* (Bacigalupo et al., 2016, p. 7).

The EntreComp Framework, referring to the definition of the 'Danish Foundation for Entrepreneurship - Young Entrepreneurs' (FFE-YE, 2012), defines entrepreneurship as: *'Entrepreneurship is when you act upon opportunities and ideas and transform them into value for others. The value that is created can be financial, cultural, or social'* (Ibid., p. 10).

The Framework focuses on the concept of 'value creation' and is applicable to all spheres of a person's life, including different meanings of the construct of entrepreneurship, through which the individual can contribute to creating value for him/herself and for society, namely: entrepreneurship, social, green and digital entrepreneurship.

The Framework is composed of three competence areas (Figure 1):

1. Ideas and Opportunities
2. Resources
3. In Action

Figure 1 – EntreComp Framework. Source: European Commission. Joint Research Centre, 2016, p. 6

Each area includes five competences that together form the entrepreneurship block as a competency model “to transform ideas and opportunities into action by mobilizing resources” (Bacigalupo et al., 2016, p. 10).

The fifteen competences are developed according to a progressive scheme of 8 levels (Figure 2), which opens into 442 learning outcomes, providing “inspiration and insight for those designing interventions from different educational contexts and domains of application” (Ibid.).

The learning outcomes, defined as ‘statements of what a learner knows, understands and is able to do after completion of learning’ (Ibid., p. 17, referring to Cedefop, 2009), are validated by ‘iterative multi-stakeholder consultations’ (Ibid., p. 6) and are declined according to a level of progression that takes into account two aspects (Ibid. p. 16):

1. Developing increasing autonomy and responsibility in acting upon ideas and opportunities to create value.
2. Developing the capacity to generate value from simple and predictable contexts up to complex, constantly changing environments.

Foundation		Intermediate		Advanced		Expert	
Relying on support ⁶ from others		Building independence		Taking responsibility		Driving transformation, innovation and growth	
Under direct supervision.	With reduced support from others, some autonomy and together with my peers.	On my own and together with my peers.	Taking and sharing some responsibilities.	With some guidance and together with others.	Taking responsibility for making decisions and working with others.	Taking responsibility for contributing to complex developments in a specific field.	Contributing substantially to the development of a specific field.
Discover	Explore	Experiment	Dare	Improve	Reinforce	Expand	Transform
Level 1 focuses mainly on discovering your qualities, potential, interests and wishes. It also focuses on recognising different types of problems and needs that can be solved creatively, and on developing individual skills and attitudes.	Level 2 focuses on exploring different approaches to problems, concentrating on diversity and developing social skills and attitudes.	Level 3 focuses on critical thinking and on experimenting with creating value, for instance through practical entrepreneurial experiences.	Level 4 focuses on turning ideas into action in ‘real life’ and on taking responsibility for this.	Level 5 focuses on improving your skills for turning ideas into action, taking increasing responsibility for creating value, and developing knowledge about entrepreneurship.	Level 6 focuses on working with others, using the knowledge you have to generate value, dealing with increasingly complex challenges.	Level 7 focuses on the competences needed to deal with complex challenges, handling a constantly changing environment where the degree of uncertainty is high.	Level 8 focuses on emerging challenges by developing new knowledge, through research and development and innovation capabilities to achieve excellence and transform the ways things are done.

Figure 2 - EntreComp Framework progression model. Source: European Commission. Joint Research Centre, 2016, p. 16

The Framework is a tool for creating a stable connection between the world of education and the world of work, thereby fostering the employability of individuals: “The framework is a flexible source of inspiration, to be used or adapted to support different contexts. For example, EntreComp could inspire the reform of curricula in the formal education and training sector, the design of practical entrepreneurial experiences in non-formal learning contexts, or the development of tools for citizens to self-assess their entrepreneurial proficiency” (Bacigalupo et al., 2016, p. 5).

GreenComp Framework

GreenComp (Bianchi et al., 2022) was developed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission as part of the policy actions set out in the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019). The framework serves as a catalyst to promote learning on environmental sustainability in

the European Union, responding to the growing need for people to improve and develop the knowledge, skills, and attitudes to live, work, and act sustainably.

The framework adopts a clear definition of sustainability as its foundation: *"Sustainability means prioritising the needs of all life forms and of the planet by ensuring that human activity does not exceed planetary boundaries"* (Bianchi et al., 2022, p. 11).

In this context, GreenComp defines a sustainability competence as one that *"empowers learners to embody sustainability values, and embrace complex systems, in order to take or request action that restores and maintains ecosystem health and enhances justice, generating visions for sustainable futures"* (Bianchi et al., 2022, p. 12).

The GreenComp framework consists of four distinct but interrelated competence areas (Figure 3):

1. Embodying sustainability values
2. Embracing complexity in sustainability
3. Envisioning sustainable futures
4. Acting for sustainability

Figure 3 – Visual representation of GreenComp. Source: GreenComp - The European sustainability competence framework, p. 6

Each competence area comprises three competences, resulting in a total of 12 sustainability competences that together form the building blocks of sustainability as a competence. The framework emphasizes that all competences are equally important and interrelated, designed to be developed across all levels of education and in any learning setting - formal, non-formal, and informal.

The framework's structure reflects the understanding that sustainability education should be transformative in nature. This aligns with UNESCO's vision that sees sustainability education as a catalyst for change among young and adult generations through the acquisition of sustainability competences (UNESCO, 2021).

Key Features of GreenComp Areas:

1. Embodying sustainability values focuses on developing empathy towards the planet, encouraging reflection on personal values and worldviews, and promoting equity and justice

- for current and future generations. This area recognizes that knowledge is not value-free and that our rationality is limited by our values and worldviews.
2. Embracing complexity in sustainability empowers learners with systemic and critical thinking capabilities. It emphasizes the interconnectedness of environmental challenges with economic activities and societal lifestyles, recognizing that environmental quality is intrinsically linked to equity and justice.
 3. Envisioning sustainable futures enables learners to visualize alternative future scenarios and identify actions to achieve a sustainable future. It encourages moving away from seeking certainties to thinking about possibilities and understanding the future as something that can be shaped collectively.
 4. Acting for sustainability encourages learners to take action at individual and collective levels to shape sustainable futures. This area recognizes that necessary transformations for sustainability are enabled not only by technological changes but also by cultural and social changes, as well as behavioral shifts and institutional reforms.

The framework is designed to be non-prescriptive and adaptable, serving as a reference tool for various purposes including curricula development, teacher education programs, and policy development. It emphasizes that while comprehensive in its coverage of sustainability competences, not all learners need to develop all competences to the highest level of proficiency.

GreenComp can be used to:

- Raise awareness about the importance of learning for environmental sustainability
- Design learning opportunities aimed at developing sustainability competences
- Assess progress in supporting education and training for sustainability
- Shape educational offerings at general, vocational, higher, and adult education levels
- Inform teacher training and continued professional development
- Guide the development of assessment and certification services

The framework acknowledges that experiencing sustainability (experiential learning) is essential to stimulate a change in mindset, which can in turn promote a change in production and consumption patterns. This approach aligns with the transformative learning theory that emphasizes profound changes in perspectives, beliefs, and behaviors through reflection on what we know and do not know.

Bloom's taxonomy

Bloom's Taxonomy represents a fundamental framework for structuring and understanding educational objectives, particularly in the context of learning outcomes-based education. Originally developed by Benjamin Bloom and colleagues in 1956, and significantly revised by Anderson and Krathwohl in 2001, the taxonomy provides a systematic approach to classifying learning objectives and promoting increasingly complex cognitive processes (Bloom et al., 1956; Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001).

The taxonomy's significance in learning outcomes-based education lies in its alignment with the European Qualifications Framework's eight levels of progression. This alignment enables educators to design learning experiences that systematically develop both foundational knowledge and advanced cognitive capabilities. The eight levels of progression, integrated with Bloom's cognitive domains, can be understood as follows:

Level 1 (Basic General Knowledge):

- Focuses on remembering and understanding basic facts
- Demonstrates simple skills under direct supervision
- Aligns with Bloom's "Remember" category, involving recognition and recall of information

Level 2 (Basic Factual Knowledge):

- Expands understanding of field-specific facts
- Develops basic cognitive and practical skills
- Corresponds to Bloom's "Understand" level, where learners explain ideas or concepts

Level 3 (Knowledge of Facts, Principles, Processes):

- Applies knowledge of facts, principles, and processes
- Takes responsibility for completing tasks
- Relates to Bloom's "Apply" category, using information in new situations

Level 4 (Factual and Theoretical Knowledge):

- Demonstrates broad theoretical and factual knowledge
- Generates solutions to specific problems
- Aligns with lower levels of Bloom's "Analyze" category

Level 5 (Comprehensive Specialized Knowledge):

- Shows comprehensive specialized knowledge
- Develops creative solutions to abstract problems
- Corresponds to higher levels of Bloom's "Analyze" and begins "Evaluate" stages

Level 6 (Advanced Knowledge of a Field):

- Masters advanced knowledge and critical understanding
- Manages complex technical or professional activities
- Fully engages Bloom's "Evaluate" category, making judgments based on criteria

Level 7 (Highly Specialized Knowledge):

- Demonstrates highly specialized knowledge
- Solves problems in research and innovation
- Begins to integrate Bloom's "Create" category with original research

Level 8 (Knowledge at the Frontier):

- Represents the most advanced frontier of knowledge
- Shows substantial authority, innovation, and autonomy
- Fully realizes Bloom's "Create" category through original research and development.

The integration of Bloom's Taxonomy with these eight levels provides what Anderson and Krathwohl (2001) describe as a comprehensive framework for designing and assessing learning outcomes. This integration is particularly relevant in competency-based frameworks, as noted by Andresen, Boud, and Cohen (2000), who emphasize the importance of structured cognitive development in experience-based learning contexts.

In the context of learning outcomes-based education, this eight-level progression serves several crucial functions:

- First, it provides a clear structure for developing learning outcomes that progress from basic comprehension to expert-level creation and innovation. As Bloom, Hasting, and Madaus (1971) demonstrate, this progression is essential for ensuring that learners develop both foundational knowledge and advanced cognitive capabilities necessary for professional practice.

- Second, the eight-level structure aligns with the European Qualifications Framework's emphasis on lifelong learning and professional development. This alignment enables educational institutions to design programs that systematically develop competencies from basic to advanced levels, ensuring that learners can progress through clearly defined stages of professional development.
- The significance of this approach lies in its ability to bridge theoretical understanding with practical application. As Bloom et al. (1974) argue, effective learning outcomes must facilitate not only the acquisition of knowledge but also its practical application in increasingly complex contexts. The eight-level progression ensures that learners develop both theoretical understanding and practical capabilities in their chosen field.
- This structured approach supports what Andresen, Boud, and Cohen (2000) identify as key elements of effective learning: the integration of theory with practice, the development of reflective capabilities, and the ability to apply learning in new contexts.

The theoretical foundations presented above - learning outcomes-oriented approach, experiential learning, EntreComp, GreenComp, and Bloom's Taxonomy - provide a comprehensive and robust scaffolding for the Framework of Competences for Students' Sustainable Entrepreneurial Mindset. These complementary theoretical perspectives work in concert to support the development of sustainable entrepreneurship competencies: learning outcomes offer the structural approach for competence development, experiential learning provides the pedagogical methodology, EntreComp and GreenComp frameworks supply the content foundations for entrepreneurship and sustainability respectively, while Bloom's Taxonomy ensures appropriate cognitive progression through clearly defined learning stages. Together, these theoretical underpinnings ensure that the framework is both academically rigorous and practically applicable in educational settings, creating a bridge between theoretical knowledge and real-world application in sustainable entrepreneurship education.

Methodology

1. Framework Integration

The first step involved a careful analysis and synthesis of the EntreComp and GreenComp frameworks. Key competences from each framework were selected based on their relevance to secondary education and their potential for integration. The selection process prioritized competences that:

- Were feasible to achieve within the VET (Vocational Education and Training) learning process and developmentally appropriate for secondary school students
- Offered clear opportunities for synergy between entrepreneurship and sustainability
- Provided a comprehensive coverage of both domains
- Were essential for a sustainable entrepreneur
- Presented an acceptable level of developmental risk for learning.

2. Structural Design

The framework was structured around five main areas, inspired by both entrepreneurship and sustainability concepts:

1. Design Thinking & Sustainability Values
2. Business Model Generation & Embracing Complexity
3. Into Action & Acting for Sustainability
4. Ideas & Opportunities & Envisioning Sustainable Futures
5. Resources & Sustainability Complexity

These areas were chosen to provide a holistic approach to sustainable entrepreneurship, covering ideation, planning, execution, and resource management, all within a sustainability context.

3. Learning Progression

For each area, a three-level progression was established:

1. Initial (Understand)
2. Intermediate (Analyze)
3. Advanced (Create)

This progression was aligned with Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives, ensuring a coherent development of cognitive skills from basic understanding to complex creation and evaluation.

4. Learning Outcomes Definition

For each level within each area, learning outcomes were defined in terms of:

- Knowledge: What students should know
- Skills: What students should be able to do
- Competence: How students should be able to apply their knowledge and skills

This tripartite structure ensures a comprehensive approach to learning, covering cognitive, practical, and attitudinal aspects of sustainable entrepreneurship.

5. Integration of EntreComp and GreenComp

A key methodological step was the careful integration of EntreComp and GreenComp competences. This process is best illustrated through an example:

In the area "Ideas & Opportunities & Envisioning Sustainable Futures":

- EntreComp competence: "Spotting opportunities"
- GreenComp competence: "Envisioning sustainable futures"

These were integrated across the three levels as follows:

Initial Level (Understand)

- Knowledge: Understand the concept of sustainable innovation and opportunity recognition.
- Skills: Identify potential sustainable business opportunities in familiar contexts.
- Competence: Imagine simple scenarios for a more sustainable future.

This level combines the EntreComp focus on understanding opportunities with the GreenComp emphasis on imagining sustainable futures.

Intermediate Level (Analyze)

- Knowledge: Analyze trends and patterns in sustainable innovation and market demands.
- Skills: Conduct basic needs analysis involving relevant stakeholders for sustainability projects.
- Competence: Evaluate and compare different sustainable future scenarios.

Here, the EntreComp skills of analyzing market trends and stakeholder engagement are combined with the GreenComp competence of evaluating sustainable scenarios.

Advanced Level (Create)

- Knowledge: Design innovative solutions that enable the creation of sustainable products
- Skills: Generate and validate innovative ideas for sustainable products or services.
- Competence: Create detailed, actionable visions for sustainable futures and develop strategies to achieve them.

At this level, the EntreComp focus on generating innovative ideas is integrated with the GreenComp emphasis on creating detailed sustainable future visions.

6. Alignment with Student Capabilities

Throughout the process, we continuously reassessed and adjusted the complexity of the framework to ensure it remained challenging yet achievable for secondary school students. This involved:

- Simplifying complex concepts
- Using familiar contexts and examples
- Focusing on practical, hands-on activities
- Ensuring a gradual progression between levels

7. Alignment with Bloom's Taxonomy

The verbs used in defining learning outcomes were carefully chosen to align with Bloom's Taxonomy:

- Initial level: "understand", "identify", "imagine" (Understand)
- Intermediate level: "analyze", "conduct", "evaluate", "compare" (Analyze)
- Advanced level: "master", "generate", "validate", "create", "develop", "design" (Create)

This ensures a clear cognitive progression from lower-order to higher-order thinking skills.

8. Development of Virtual Simulation Platform

To apply the framework in a practical way, we developed a virtual simulation platform focused on sustainable entrepreneurship in the smart clothing sector. Key features that guided its development include:

- Branching scenarios aligned with the areas and levels of the framework
- Integration of the platform with scenarios developed in XR
- AI-powered progress tracking
- Personalized feedback and learning resources

9. Scenario Development

We created scenarios for each level within each framework area. For example, for "Resources & Sustainability Complexity" at smart clothing distribution companies:

- Beginner-Level Scenario: students list the characteristics that biodegradable packaging for their products should have.
- Intermediate-Level Scenario: students compare different packaging options, according to the characteristics identified.
- Advanced-Level Scenario: students create a reusable packaging selection model in a sustainability workshop at their school.

10. Iterative Refinement

Throughout the development process, we continuously refined both the framework and the simulation platform concept based on:

- Feedback on the appropriateness for secondary students
- Alignment with learning outcomes
- Practical applicability in a virtual learning environment

Challenges and Solutions

A key challenge was balancing the complexity of sustainable entrepreneurship concepts with the cognitive capabilities of secondary school students. We addressed this by:

1. Simplifying advanced concepts without losing their essence
2. Using relatable examples and contexts
3. Providing a clear, gradual progression in complexity
4. Focusing on practical application rather than theoretical understanding

Preliminary Reflections

The resulting framework and virtual simulation platform concept provide a comprehensive, theoretically grounded, and practically oriented approach to developing a sustainable entrepreneurial mindset in secondary school students. The framework integrates key competences from EntreComp and GreenComp, structured in a way that promotes progressive learning and aligns with established educational theories, while remaining accessible and engaging for the target age group.

This framework offers educators a tool to foster both entrepreneurial skills and sustainability awareness, preparing students to address complex real-world challenges with creativity, innovation, and a strong sense of environmental and social responsibility.

Future work will involve piloting this framework in secondary school settings, gathering feedback from educators and students, and refining the learning outcomes based on practical implementation experiences. The iterative approach will ensure that the framework and platform remain relevant, effective, and aligned with the evolving needs of sustainable entrepreneurship education for secondary school students.

References

1. Anderson, L. W., & Krathwohl, D. R. (Eds.). (2001). *A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives* (Complete ed.). Longman.
2. Andresen, L., Boud, D., & Cohen, R. (2000). Experience-Based Learning. In G. Foley (Ed.), *Understanding Adult Education and Training* (pp. 225-239). Allen & Unwin.
3. Bacigalupo, M., Kamylyis, P., Punie, Y., Brande, G. V. den, European Commission, & Joint Research Centre. (2016). *EntreComp: The entrepreneurship competence framework*. Publications Office. <http://dx.publications.europa.eu/10.2791/593884>

4. Bianchi, G., Pisiotis, U., & Cabrera Giraldez, M. (2022). *GreenComp - The European sustainability competence framework*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/13286>
5. Bloom, B. S. (Ed.). (1956). *Taxonomy of educational objectives: The classification of educational goals. Handbook 1: Cognitive domain*. David McKay Company.
6. Bloom, B. S., Engelhart, M. D., Furst, E. J., Hill, W. H., & Krathwohl, D. R. (1974). *Taxonomy of educational objectives: The classification of educational goals. Handbook 1: Cognitive domain*. David McKay.
7. Bloom, B. S., Hastings, J. T., & Madaus, G. F. (1971). *Handbook on formative and summative evaluation of student learning*. McGraw-Hill.
8. Boud, D., Cohen, R., & Walker, D. (1993). *Using experience for learning*. Society for Research into Higher Education and Open University Press.
9. Cedefop. (2009). *The shift to learning outcomes: Policies and practices in Europe*. Cedefop Reference series. Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.
10. Cedefop. (2017). *Defining, writing and applying learning outcomes: A European handbook*. Publications Office of the European Union.
11. Council of the European Union. (2017). Council Recommendation of 22 May 2017 on the European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning. *Official Journal of the European Union*, C189/15.
12. Dewey, J. (1938). *Experience and education*. Macmillan.
13. European Commission. (2016). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: A New Skills Agenda for Europe. Working together to strengthen human capital, employability and competitiveness. COM(2016)381 final. Publications Office of the European Union.
14. European Commission. (2019). *The European Green Deal*. COM(2019) 640 final. European Commission.
15. European Parliament and Council of the European Union. (2006). Recommendation of 18 December 2006 on key competences for lifelong learning (2006/962/EC). *Official Journal of the European Union*.
16. FFE-YE. (2012). Impact of entrepreneurship education in Denmark - 2011. In L. Vestergaard, K. Moberg & C. Jørgensen (Eds.). *The Danish Foundation for Entrepreneurship - Young Enterprise*.
17. Jarvis, P. (2006). *Towards a comprehensive theory of human learning*. Routledge.
18. Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development*. Prentice Hall.
19. Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.
20. Mezirow, J. (1991). *Transformative dimensions of adult learning*. Jossey-Bass.
21. Moon, J. A. (2004). *A handbook of reflective and experiential learning: Theory and practice*. RoutledgeFalmer.
22. Schön, D. A. (1983). *The reflective practitioner: How professionals think in action*. Basic Books.
23. UNESCO. (2021). *Learn for our planet: A global review of how environmental issues are integrated in education*. UNESCO.
24. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.

Framework for Sustainable Entrepreneurial Mindset in Secondary Education

1. Design Thinking & Sustainability Values

Initial (Understand)

- **Knowledge:** Understand the basic principles of design thinking and sustainability.
- **Skills:** Identify sustainability challenges in the local community.
- **Competence:** Recognize the value of sustainable ideas in entrepreneurship.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students are presented with a typical smart clothing distribution process and asked to identify potential sustainability issues in packaging, transportation, and inventory management (a virtual tour of a smart clothing distribution center and asked to identify potential sustainability issues in the distribution process).

Intermediate (Analyze)

- **Knowledge:** Analyze the interconnections between design thinking, sustainability, and business opportunities.
- **Skills:** Apply design thinking methods to frame sustainability problems.
- **Competence:** Critically evaluate how personal values align with sustainability principles in business contexts.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students analyze the main stages of smart clothing distribution (warehousing, order fulfillment, last-mile delivery) and apply design thinking methods to propose one eco-friendly improvement for each stage, considering both environmental impact and customer experience.

Advanced (Create)

- **Knowledge:** Integrate advanced design thinking concepts with sustainability frameworks.
- **Skills:** Create innovative solutions for sustainability challenges using design thinking methodologies.
- **Competence:** Develop a personal ethical framework that balances entrepreneurial goals with sustainability values.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students design an innovative distribution system for smart clothing that integrates cutting-edge technology with circular economy principles, focusing on sustainable packaging, efficient logistics, and product lifecycle management.

2. Business Model Generation & Embracing Complexity

Initial (Understand)

- **Knowledge:** Comprehend basic business model components and their relation to sustainability.
- **Skills:** Identify key stakeholders in a simple sustainable business model.
- **Competence:** Recognize the complexity of sustainability issues in business contexts.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students identify key stakeholders in the smart clothing distribution network, focusing on the roles involved in getting products from manufacturers to end consumers.

Intermediate (Analyze)

- **Knowledge:** Understand the principles of circular economy and their application in business models.
- **Skills:** Analyze how different business model elements interact with sustainability factors.
- **Competence:** Apply systems thinking to evaluate the sustainability of a business model.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students analyze how introducing reusable packaging for smart clothing deliveries affects different parts of the distribution business, such as shipping costs, customer satisfaction, and environmental impact.

Advanced (Create)

- **Knowledge:** Master advanced concepts of sustainable business model innovation.
- **Skills:** Develop comprehensive, sustainable business models that address complex environmental and social issues.
- **Competence:** Create adaptive strategies to manage sustainability challenges in uncertain business environments.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students develop a sustainable business model for a local smart clothing distribution company. The model focuses on three main areas: Eco-friendly packaging and shipping methods; A product repair and refurbishment service to extend clothing lifespan; A local partnership program for efficient last-mile delivery.

3. Into Action & Acting for Sustainability

Initial (Understand)

- **Knowledge:** Understand basic project management principles for sustainable initiatives.
- **Skills:** Set simple goals and milestones for a sustainable project.
- **Competence:** Recognize personal potential to contribute to sustainability through entrepreneurial action.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students set basic sustainability goals for launching a new smart clothing distribution service in their local area.

Intermediate (Analyze)

- **Knowledge:** Analyze different approaches to implement sustainable business practices.
- **Skills:** Evaluate risks and opportunities in sustainable entrepreneurship projects.
- **Competence:** Collaborate effectively with diverse stakeholders on sustainability initiatives.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students evaluate risks and opportunities in implementing a sustainable last-mile delivery program for smart clothing distribution, considering electric vehicles and optimized routes.

Advanced (Create)

- **Knowledge:** Master advanced techniques for measuring and reporting sustainability impact.
- **Skills:** Develop and implement comprehensive plans for sustainable value creation.
- **Competence:** Lead and inspire others in collective action for sustainability entrepreneurship.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students develop and pitch a comprehensive plan for transforming an existing smart clothing distribution company into a sustainability leader, including circular packaging systems, and innovative last-mile delivery solutions using eco-friendly technologies.

4. Ideas & Opportunities & Envisioning Sustainable Futures

Initial (Understand)

- **Knowledge:** Understand the concept of sustainable innovation and opportunity recognition.
- **Skills:** Identify potential sustainable business opportunities in familiar contexts.
- **Competence:** Imagine simple scenarios for a more sustainable future.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students identify potential sustainable innovations in smart clothing distribution that could address local environmental challenges.

Intermediate (Analyze)

- **Knowledge:** Analyze trends and patterns in sustainable innovation and market demands.
- **Skills:** Conduct basic needs analysis involving relevant stakeholders for sustainability projects.
- **Competence:** Evaluate and compare different sustainable future scenarios.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students conduct a needs analysis for sustainable smart clothing distribution services in a specific urban area, considering various stakeholders and local sustainability challenges.

Advanced (Create)

- **Knowledge:** Design innovative solutions that enable the creation of sustainable products.
- **Skills:** Generate and validate innovative ideas for sustainable products or services.
- **Competence:** Create detailed, actionable visions for sustainable futures and develop strategies to achieve them.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students create a detailed vision for the future of sustainable smart clothing distribution and develop comprehensive strategies to achieve it, focusing on innovative last-mile delivery solutions, circular packaging systems.

5. Resources & Sustainability Complexity

Initial (Understand)

- **Knowledge:** Recognize basic resources needed in simple business operations (e.g., materials, energy, water).
- **Skills:** Identify ways to save resources in a simple sustainable project.
- **Competence:** Explain the importance of using resources responsibly in a business context.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students list the characteristics that biodegradable packaging for their products should have and provide examples on the use of recyclable and sustainable packaging for smart clothing.

Intermediate (Analyze)

- **Knowledge:** Understand the concept of resource efficiency and its importance in sustainable business practices.
- **Skills:** Compare the resource use of two similar products or services.
- **Competence:** Suggest improvements for resource use in a familiar setting (e.g., classroom, school cafeteria).

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students compare different materials and process options, according to the characteristics identified.

Advanced (Create)

- **Knowledge:** Understand the basics of circular economy as applied to a simple business or school project.
- **Skills:** Develop a simple plan to reduce waste or improve resource use in a school or community activity.
- **Competence:** Create and present a basic proposal for a small-scale sustainable project that uses resources efficiently.

Example for the virtual learning scenarios in the context of the smart clothing sector: Students create a circular economy model for the smart distribution of clothing, focusing on reusable packaging and efficient reverse logistics and present at their school the various alternatives (business options) based on the references and investigation carried out at the "Initial" and "Intermediate" levels, in a competition that will award the best proposal presented.

Framework of Competences for the students' "Sustainable Entrepreneurial Mindset"

November 2024

Authors of the report

Erina Guraziu, Phd; Rodrigo Latorre Vivar, Phd

Partner Coordinator

OpenCom

Collaborating Partners

Lounais-Hämeen koulutuskuntayhtymä (FI)

Raija Salo

Karita Stenfors-Selkälä

Sanni Pylkkönen

OpenCom (IT)

Fabio Frangipani

Ilenia Costa

Technological University of Dublin (IE)

Aidan Kenny

ORTAKÖY 80.YIL MESLEKİ ve TEKNİK ANADOLU LİSESİ(TK)

Ercan Küçükarslan

Ahmet Okan YAVUZ

Centro de Formación Internacional Reina Isabel (ES)

Jesús Porrúa Ávila

Virginia Lechuga Justicia

Rocío Molina Molina

Purificación Revelles Aguilera

Praktica Training and Consulting (ES)

Paula Medina Nieto

Marién Pérez López

I.I.S. "Benvenuto Cellini" (IT)

Carlo Stella

Claudia Benelli

Ufficio Scolastico Regionale per la Toscana (IT)

Antonietta Marini

Teresa Madeo

Maria Teresa Tronfi

Daniela Cecchi

Euro Education Bulgaria (BG)
Marinela Yordanova

3DBear Oy (FI)
Alisa Ilola
Pekka Salokannel
Anna Rantapero-Laine

Special Thanks.

We extend our sincere gratitude to the following distinguished experts and organizations whose thorough evaluation and valuable feedback have significantly enhanced the quality of this framework:

Forssa Fabric Oy/Rykkeri Finland

Acknowledgement

This report is a deliverable of the project “Sustainable Entrepreneurship in Smart Clothing”, funded within the Erasmus+ Programme with applicant: Lounais-Hämeen koulutuskuntayhtymä (FI).

Grant Agreement No. 2023-1-FI01-KA220-VET-000160581

SEiSC

Sustainable
Entrepreneurship
in Smart Clothing

2023-1-FI01-KA220-VET-000160581

01.11.2023 > 31.10.2026

Framework of competences for the students’ “Sustainable Entrepreneurial Mindset”

November 2024

Co-funded by
the European Union

Views and opinions expressed are, however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Erasmus+ Agency. Neither the European Union nor Erasmus+ Agency can be held responsible for them.